

Motion Planning In Certain Lexicographic Product Graphs

A. D Akwu¹ And O. Oyewumi²

¹ Department of mathematics, federal university of agriculture, makurdi, Nigeria

² Air Force Institute Of Technology, Kaduna, Nigeria.

Email: abolaopeyemi@yahoo.co.uk, opeyemioluwaoyewumi@gmail.com

Abstract:

Let t be an undirected graph with n vertices in which a robot is placed at a vertex say v , and a hole at vertex u and in all other $(n - 2)$ vertices are obstacles. We refer to this assignment of robot and obstacles as a configuration C_v of t . Suppose we have a one player game in which the robot or obstacle can be slide to an adjacent vertex if it is empty i.e. if it has a hole. The goal is to take the robot to a particular destination vertex using minimum number of moves. In this article, we give the minimum number of moves required for the motion planning problem in Lexicographic products of some graphs.

Keywords:

Robot motion in a graph, Lexicographic product of graphs, k -factor of graphs,

References:

- [1] V. Auletta, A. Monti, M. Parente, and P. Persiano, A linear time algorithm for the feasibility of pebble motions on trees, Proceedings of Scandinavian Workshop on Algorithm Theory, (SWAT) Lecture Notes in Computer Science 1097, pages 259-270, 1996.
- [2] V. Auletta and P. Persiano, Optimal pebble motion on a tree. Information and Computation, 165:42-68, February 2001.
- [3] B. Deb, K. Kapoor, Motion planning in Cartesian product graphs, Disc. Math. Graph Theory 34 (2014) 207-221
- [4] B. Deb, K. Kapoor, On Motion planning in Graphs, Ph.D thesis, Indian Institute of Technology, Guwahati, 2012.
- [5] M. Ellips and H. Azadeh, Solvability of multi robot motion planning problems on trees. In Intelligent Robots and Systems, 2009. IROS 2009. IEEE/RSJ International Conference on, pages 5936-5941, Oct. 2009.

A Review of Developments in Field Robots for Agricultural applications: History, Present trends and Design challenges

Dr. Alkali Babawuya^{1*}, Ibrahim Suleimen²

¹Department of Mechatronics Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Minna

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal Polytechnics, Bida

Email: babawuya@futminna.edu.ng

Abstract:

Robots are used in various fields to carry out different functions, they are used for simple to even impossible tasks that cannot be handled by human beings. Interest in robotics is steadily rising with the availability of cheaper and smaller electronic components. The application of robots in farms is numerous, they are used to control pests and weed, manage crop health, augment labour shortages, curtail resource waste and solve environmental damage due to use of heavy machinery. This paper presents a review of the developments in agricultural field robots, the history, the present trends in the field and subsequently challenges such as the dynamic farm environment, the path planning and navigation problem is discussed. Current state of developed robots is also briefly highlighted.

Keywords:

Bird-pest, mobil-robot, agricultural-robots, design challenges, mapping, automonous robot.

Biography:

Dr. Alkali Babawuya (Born February 25th, 1976) received his first and second degrees in Mechanical Engineering (Design and Solid Mechanics Options) from Federal University of Technology, Minna-Nigeria and PhD (2016) in Mechanical Engineering from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria-Nigeria. His currently a senior lecturer with the department of Mechatronics engineering, Federal University of technology, Minna-Nigeria. His research interest includes areas mechatronics system design and Simulation, Optimization. Good with software and hardware programming. He has couples of international conferences attendance and Journal publication. He is also a register engineering with council for registration of engineering in Nigeria (COREN). He is married and has three children (Ummymah, Meenat and Fatima).

Kinematic Analysis Of A Robotic Hand For Grasping And Manipulation Tasks

Dr. Eram Neha

Assistant Professor in the Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Galgotia College of Engineering and Technology, Noida, India

Email: eram.neha@galgotiacollege.edu

Abstract:

Multi-finger Robotic hands (MFRH) are desired similar to human hands in order to perform stable grasping and fine manipulation of different objects. Their industrial applications including material handling fulfills the requirement of unique end-effector tool empowering specific reach, payloads, and flexibility. The design and control of dexterous and prosthetic robotic hands is of important concern these days. The performance of these hands depends on their mechanical design, prosthetics etc. The mechanical range of movement must be properly controlled and monitored to get the best performance of the robotic hand.

A newly designed tendon actuated robotic hand is discussed along with its mechanical structure. Multi-finger robotic hands are analyzed in comparison with human hands in terms of stable grasping and fine manipulation of different objects. Therefore, in order to attain a stable grasp, the contact points and the grip configuration must be selected in accordance with the grasp stability. The robotic hand is simulated to grasp different objects and determine the contact points of the fingertips on the surface of these objects. The obtained contact points are validated using the kinematics and geometric collision detection. These contact points are further utilized experimentally to determine the amount of weight required by the tendon to produce the flexion motion in order to grasp the object at the contact points.

Keywords:

ABS, polyamide, Nylon, 3D printing, kinematics and geometric collision detection.

Biography:

Dr. Eram Neha is presently employed as Assistant Professor in the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Galgotia College of Engineering and Technology, Greater Noida. She has pursued her B.Tech in Mechanical Engineering from MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, India. She has obtained her M.Tech in CAD/CAM & Robotics from Thapar University, Patiala, Punjab, India. Thereafter she obtained her Ph.D from Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India in the area of Kinematic Studies on 4-finger tendon actuated robotic hand. Her areas of interest are Robotics, Robot Programming, Design & Development of Multi-finger Robotic Hands, Trajectory Planning, Manipulability Analysis, 3D Visualization of Model in Virtual Environments, Kinematic and Dynamic Analysis, Modelling and simulation, control system, Computer Aided Design and Computer Aided manufacturing. She has also been awarded the merit based Maulana Azad National fellowship at the JRF and SRF level for her research. She has published around 15 papers in National/International Journals and Conferences of repute. She is also a professional member of The Robotic Society.

System and Method for Stress Estimation and Drowsiness Detection using single RGB Camera

Ms. Ankita Kalra

Carnegie Mellon University, USA

Email: ankitakalra@cmu.edu

Abstract:

Abstract:

Stress, defined as any kind of disturbance in physiological homeostasis[??], is omnipresent in modern day life. In this work, we describe ongoing experiments on Stress Estimation and Drowsiness Detection using an RGB camera based on two types of features: (1)Heart-rate variability (HRV) as derived from the heart rate estimated using a non-contact method (2) Eye closure, saccadic eye movements and gaze (3) Facial expressions. The eye closure and movement percentage, and facial expression change frequency are determined using computer vision technique based on active shape model. The HRV is used to extract a physiological stress and sleepiness metric. This combination has the advantage that it reduces false alarms raised by systems that solely rely on eye closure based measures. For preliminary experiments, it is observed that there is a significant correlation between the two metrics. The proposed method has the advantage that only a single RGB camera is required for Drowsiness detection and Stress Estimation. The experiments were conducted in workplace, we motivate this work to be used in more vital scenarios like driving assist Insurance premium calculation based on behavioural data, construction sites and hospitals.

Keywords:

Stress estimation, heart rate variability

Hierarchical classification using Conditional SOM and its application to situation Analysis

Dr. Jaiprakash Narain Dwivedi

Associate Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
Affiliated to Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Hyderabad, India.

Email: jpndwivedi@gmail.com

Abstract:

My research was focused on the hierarchical classification using Conditional Self-Organizing Map and its application to situation analysis. Situation includes the vehicle arrangements on the different shapes of the road. The preparation of limited number of situations to prepare set of rules for the prediction of root cause of collision during autonomous driving. To achieve this task, the discretization or quantization, so to say clustering or classification is needed. To fulfill this requirement, the hierarchical classification of the different kind of shapes of the road and objects corresponding to them has been considered as appropriate approach.

In an experiment and for the first step of hierarchy of the situation classification, the data considered are the different shapes of the road. These different shapes of the road are cross junction (i.e. four way road), T-junction (i.e. three way road) and straight road. The dot distribution representation is used throughout for the representation of the shapes of the road data. The variation among shapes has been observed using U matrix. The TFSOM x SOM (i.e. Topology Free Self-Organizing Map by Self Organizing Map) algorithm [1] has been considered as an approach of classification of the different shapes of the road.

A vehicle trajectory has been drawn on these different shapes of the road with the first step of hierarchy of situation classification. Let us understand with an example. Suppose a road starts from point A to point B and between point A and point B, a combination of all the three different shapes of the road discussed above is available. From point A to point B, a vehicle coordinates have also been observed to track the position of vehicle along with the coordinates of the road. As the vehicle starts travelling from point A, it has to pass through the straight road, cross shapes of the road and T-junction shape of the road till the end of travel i.e. up to point B. To obtain all the different shapes of the road as a simulation result, we included the concept the standard deviation. The standard deviation concept was used as a penalty term because without using this penalty term, we were not able to get the required three different shapes of the road. For the simulation, the three different shapes of the road are provided as the input and as an output, we plotted three shapes of the road in three different color in order to recognize different shapes of the road comfortably.

In another experiment and for the second step of hierarchy of the situation classification, the data considered are the coordinates of the vehicles on the road. In this time, only cross shapes of the road are being considered as the coordinates of shape of the road. This is because that the possibility of number of objects is more than that of T-junction and straight road. Thus the potential of complexity of the shapes of the road defines the risk of collision. The dot distribution representation is used throughout for the representation of the cross shapes of the road data. In this experiment, the first kind of data is the road data i.e. cross shape road data, being classified with the TFSOM x SOM algorithm as explained above. The second kind of data are the object data i.e. vehicle data being used with proposed method Conditional Self Organizing Map i.e. CSOM algorithm. The comparison of the simulation results of this proposed CSOM algorithm with the SOM (hierarchical and non-hierarchical) algorithm has been shown in order to justify that the use of this proposed CSOM algorithm is more suitable than those SOM algorithms. The quantization error is the average distance between the input data vector and its best matching unit. The simulation result of the quantization error of both CSOM algorithm and hierarchical SOM algorithm has been shown in order to justify the relevance of the proposed CSOM algorithm over hierarchical SOM algorithm. This quantization error shows that for same quantization error CSOM method needs almost one third number of learning data in comparison to that of hierarchical SOM algorithm. Also the quantization error of CSOM algorithm is lower than that of hierarchical SOM algorithm. The purpose of hierarchical classification was to anticipate the level of density of available objects (i.e. vehicles arrangement) on the road. These results will be helpful to prepare the set of rules for the prediction of root cause of collision during autonomous driving.

I believe that my research on the autonomous vehicle is very suitable for real world application. This practical approach of research will be beneficial for the academic purpose as well as future research purposes.

Keywords:

CSOM algorithm, hierarchical SOM algorithm, Pattern recognition, Artificial Neural Network, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Artificial Intelligence

References:

- [1] Jaiprakash Narain Dwivedi, Hiroaki Koga, Tetsuo Furukawa and Keiichi Horio, “Road Shape Clustering for Analysis of Collision Risk of Autonomous Vehicle”, in press ICIC Express letter B Appl, 2016.
- [2] Jaiprakash Narain Dwivedi, Hiroaki Koga, Tetsuo Furukawa and Keiichi Horio, “Hierarchical Classification Using Conditional Self-Organizing Map And Its Application To Situation Analysis” accepted in International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information and Control, 2017.

Biography:

Dr. Jaiprakash Narain Dwivedi is currently working as an Associate Professor at the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Malla Reddy Institute of Technology and Science, Affiliated to Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Hyderabad, India. Received his B.E. (Electronics and Communication Engineering) degree from Rajeev Gandhi Proudhyogiki Vishwavidyalaya Bhopal, India, M.Tech. (Signal Processing) degree from Guru Govind Singh Indraprastha University, Delhi, India and Ph.D. (Artificial Neural Network) from Graduate school of life science and system Engineering. Kyushu Institute of Technology Japan. The interest of research includes Machine Learning, Artificial Neural Network, Pattern Recognition and Classification.

A Cognitive Rehabilitation Robot for Autism Children

Dr. Jiaming Zhang^{1,2}

¹Institute of robotics and intelligent Manufacturing, The Chinese University of Hong Kong (Shenzhen), Shenzhen, China

²Shenzhen Institute of Artificial Intelligence and Robotics for Society, Shenzhen, China

Email: zhangjiaming@cuhk.edu.cn

Abstract:

Robot-enhanced therapy has a great potential in improving the performance of participants on the three levels (behavioral, cognitive, and subjective). Simon Baron-Cohen's E-S (Empathizing-Systemizing) Theory suggests that, compared with human beings, highly structured information processing systems such as robots, are more likely to be understood and communicated with for people with ASD (Autism Spectrum Disorder). Therefore, these systems can be used in cognitive intervention for ASD subjects to learn social cues such as facial expressions, hand and body gestures, verbal describing, and social touch of other people. Our study aims to introduce a novel and affordable socially interactive robot, so-called DaBao, to improve the effectiveness of rehabilitation training and the diversification of autism treatment. In this talk, I will describe how our cognitive rehabilitation robot can provide robot-mediated intervention for children with ASD. For instance, ASD children can learn to recognize and understand human facial expressions through DaBao's facial expressions and a Facial Emotion Cognition and Training System installed on the robot adopting a deep-learning algorithm for facial expression recognition and an algorithm for attention analysis of the ASD children's gaze and head directions; they can learn to associate different

touching patterns with different social meanings when they touch different parts of the robot covered by many smart Tactile Sensing Arrays; they can learn to chat verbally with the robot adopting a deep-learning algorithm for image caption that allows the robot to know what a ASD child is focusing on and to select an appropriate topic to chat about, and a general Chinese Chatbot based on deep-learning NLP; they can learn to imitate or interact with DaBao's gestures, as the robot can detect, recognize or imitate the gestures of those children.

Insights of several preliminary clinical studies involving some ASD children and our robot, will also be shared with during the talk.

Keywords:

Cognitive Rehabilitation Robots, Socially Interactive Robots, Autism Rehabilitation, Robot-enhanced Therapy, Robot-Mediated Intervention.

Biography:

Dr. Jiaming ZHANG joined the Neurocomputing and Robotics Group led by Prof. Noel Sharkey and Dr. Amanda J.C. Sharkey, in the Department of Computer Science, University of Sheffield in October, 2008, and completed his Ph.D. in Computer Science in Spring, 2013. Since then he conducted research in Affective Computing, Human-robot Interaction, Robot-enhanced Therapy and so on. He has co-led an ITC (Innovation and Technology Commission, Hong Kong) funded project-Intelligent Robotic Technologies for Treatment of Dementia in the Elderly, outcoming four generations of panda-shape robots. He is currently leading a Shenzhen Science and Technology Innovation Commission funded project-Research on Key Technologies of Animal-shape Intelligent Interactive Robots for Rehabilitation Therapy, aiming to develop robots for autism children.

Trajectory tracking and Impedance Control of Hybrid Manipulators.

Dr. Rashmi Arora

Associate Professor in Chandigarh University, Gharuan (Mohali), Punjab, India

Email: rashmimech.cu@gmail.com

Abstract:

Robotics is an exciting, dynamic interdisciplinary field of study. Industrial robots are generally referred as robotic manipulators. Since, the aim of the manipulator is the manipulative task and it is generally identified as the mechanical sub-system due to which a robot has the mechanical capability. According to the connectivity of kinematics in the structural design of the manipulators, these are classified into two types, namely serial manipulator and parallel manipulator. Usually, industrial robots are made up of serial manipulator architecture with cantilever type structure having large workspace but these suffer from several drawbacks such as low accuracy and heavy structural vibration. Similarly, the parallel architecture robots have better accuracy but small workspace. Therefore, in the last two decades, hybrid manipulators addressed great attention as a combination of serial and parallel chain architectures. In an effort to combine the advantages of serial and parallel chains in these manipulators, a brief introduction of hybrid manipulators is discussed here. These manipulators offer the possibility of having advantages of both architectures and reduce their drawbacks. A three dimensional hybrid manipulator with six degrees-of-freedom is proposed and this manipulator is made by placing a three degrees-of-freedom parallel manipulator over the other in series so as to increase its workspace and load carrying capacity. The forward and inverse dynamic models for planar hybrid manipulator as well as for 3D hybrid manipulator are developed. All the models are simulated in bond graph domain. The planar hybrid manipulator is validated for a practical application of lateral bending of human vertebrae and the path followed by the thumb of human hand while picking and placing an object. The 3D hybrid manipulator is also tested for trajectory tracking of the thumb of human hand during drawing an arc on white board with a marker pen. The physical models for planar parallel and hybrid manipulators are also reduced with Eigen value sensitivity method to reduce simulation time and complexity of the system. The response of reduced models is compared with full models to track a circular path. The workspace analysis of planar parallel and hybrid manipulators is done additionally and this illustrates that workspace is increased by connecting two parallel manipulators than a single parallel manipulator. Afterwards, the theory of impedance control with some changes is applied for an operation on a three dimensional L-shaped and M-shaped path having some restrictions imposed on the interactive forces when the manipulator is interacting with an object in its environment along with an approach to eliminate amnesia. Finally, scope for future research work will be shown.

Keywords:

Hybrid manipulator; Trajectory Tracking; overwhelming control; model order reduction; work space analysis; impedance control; bond graph

Biography:

Dr. Rashmi Arora, is working as Associate Professor in Chandigarh University, Gharuan (Mohali), Punjab, India since July 2019. Before that, she worked as Assistant Professor in Chandigarh University, Gharuan (Mohali), Punjab, India for 3 years. She had also worked at prestigious institutes like Thapar Institute of Engineering and Technology, Patiala, Punjab, India and other engineering colleges in Punjab and Haryana. She have more than 10 years of teaching experience. She also worked as a Training Engineer in Ideas Design Solution Pvt. Ltd., Gurgaon for 7 months. Regarding my education, she completed PhD in Mechanical Engineering from Thapar Institute of Engineering and Technology (Deemed to be University), Patiala (Punjab), India in July 2018 under the supervision of Dr. Tarun Kumar Bera. The research area for PhD was hybrid manipulators and title of my PhD thesis was Trajectory Tracking and Impedance Control of Hybrid Manipulators. She completed Masters of Engineering in CAD/CAM & Robotics from Thapar Institute of Engineering and Technology (Deemed to be University), Patiala (Punjab), India in 2008.

Industry 4.0: Risks and opportunities in its deployment

Dr. Sebastian J. Brau

Industry 4.0-Expert Robotics Engineer in iLEAN industrial Systems, Spain

Email: s.brau@ilean.us

Abstract:

Humanity has already experienced three major industrial revolutions throughout its history. The First Industrial Revolution appeared in the second half of 18th century, with the entrance of machinery powered by steam, which allowed the transition to industrialization. The Second Industrial Revolution took place in the half of 19th century, and it introduced machinery powered by electricity and mass production. The Third Industrial Revolution began during the 1970s, due to the entry of communication and information technologies and some level of automation.

Now, we are about to enter to the Fourth Industrial Revolution, also known as Industry 4.0. An age marked by hyperconnectivity, which means connectivity of all the assets of an organization to obtain and analyze valuable data that leads to better business decisions. It also brings digital transformation technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), Machine Learning (ML), Big Data, and more.

Our biggest concern about Industry 4.0 is not technology itself, but the pace of change within the industrial sector that could lead to a great economic and social catastrophe if we do not act on time to prevent millions of people losing their jobs due to substitution by robotic and automated systems, and not having the opportunity to get a new one.

That is the reason why we have our stake on an Industry 4.0 for Human Empowering. Our premise behind this is that, if we leverage the “brain” of a robotic system, in other words, its AI, our organizations could have an assistant on the shop floor, which can become a profitable alternative that, instead of replacing human workers, empowers their performance and frees them to put their efforts on higher value tasks.

Keywords:

Industry 4.0, Artificial Intelligence, IoT, Big Data, Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Future of Work, Digital Transformation, Lean Manufacturing.

References:

Brau, S. (2016) Lean Manufacturing 4.0, the Technological Evolution of Lean. In Press.

Design Of Sensor Unit To Count The Mould Rotations In The Electronic Pinhole Testing Machine

Shivoh Chirayil Nandakumar

University of Glasgow, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,
Glasgow, UK

Email: cnshivoh@gmail.com

Abstract:

The efficiency of the industry heavily depends on the bottlenecks in the testing departments. The main testing method for condoms and similar specimens is done in the Electronic Testing Department. The Electronic Testing Department inspect each condom for holes and thus assures the quality of product. In the testing section of the Electronic Pinhole Testing Machine, the mould rotation is a crucial process for effectively detecting the good product from the bad product. Thus, sensing mould rotations is essential for assuring the quality of testing. The difficulty to design the sensor unit is due to the fact that the moulds are simultaneously moving linearly in a chain as well as rotating on their respective axis. Currently in factories, the mould rotation is checked manually by the supervisors, this is arduous task as well as inefficient. My project is aimed at designing a sensor unit for the detection of mould rotation as well as count the number of rotations inside the testing section.

Keywords:

Electronic Testing Department, Electronic Pinhole Testing Machine, quality of product, detection, sensor unit, mould rotation.

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the 3-D model of the Flap unit. The specimen is passed through the flap unit to differentiate the good and bad specimen. The sensor unit I designed will get incorporated into this flap unit to maximize the efficiency of this unit as well as count the mould rotations while the moulds pass through the flap unit.

References:

1. Engineering Mechanics by S.S.Bhavikatti
2. Signal Processing for Communications by Paolo Prandoni and Martin Vetterli